

One-pot Synthesis of 2,5-Diphenylpyrazine

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2,5-Diphenylpyrazine and its derivatives have attracted a lot of attention as monomers for heteroaromatic polymers, as materials for liquid crystals¹ and electroluminescent devices². A variety of synthetic approaches for preparation of the title compound have been developed³⁻⁵. However, these procedures are beset with a variety of problems such as the use of not readily available starting materials, drastic conditions and low yields.

This communication describes a convenient method of preparation of 2,5-diphenylpyrazine (2) in good yield by photolysis of 3-phenylisoxazol-5-one (1) at 300 nm in methanol as solvent (Scheme 1). The starting 3-phenylisoxazol-5-one was easily prepared from the commercially available ethyl benzoylacetate⁶.

Scheme 1

The product has been identified as 2,5-diphenylpyrazine on the basis of spectral data and its comparison with the literature values⁴. The structure of 2 has been arrived mainly through the molecular ion (at m/z 232) and the fact that there are no signals in the aliphatic region in pmr and ¹³C nmr spectra. Pmr spectrum shows a signal in downfield at δ 9.0, accountable to the protons of pyrazine.

The photoconversion can be rationalised in terms of the initial cleavage of the weakest N-O linkage of the substrate⁷. The diradical generated suffers decarboxylation to give 1,3-diradical which undergoes cyclodimerisation giving the pyrazine skeleton. The transformation is completed by the oxidation of the dihydropyrazine. This can be likened to the observations of Boyer and Mikol^{3,4} who reported the formation of pyrazine from β -styrylisocyanate (Scheme 2).

This reaction has also been attempted to examine the possibility of a thermal reaction by refluxing 3-phenylisoxazol-5-one in methanol for 24 h in which there was no formation of 2,5-diphenylpyrazine. The present investigation is the first transformation of isoxazole to

Scheme 2

pyrazine reported by a photochemical method. This procedure provides direct access to 2,5-diphenylpyrazine in a one-step process, and is competitive with previously reported syntheses³⁻⁵ of the system.

Experimental

2,5-Diphenylpyrazine (2): A solution of 3-phenylisoxazol-5-one (0.5 g in 75 ml dry methanol) was irradiated for 7 h with a RUL 3000 Å lamps in a multilamp Rayonet RPR-208 reactor. Ice-cold water was circulated through a cold finger immersed in the quartz tube. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue chromatographed over silica gel (35 g). Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (20 : 80) gave a white crystalline solid, (0.24 g, 67%), m.p. 198° (lit.⁸ 197.3°).

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